

THE ANTECEDENTS OF CASH WAQF INTENTION IN INDONESIA AND MALAYSIA: A BIBLIOMETRIC AND SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW (SLR)

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Abstract: *Due to its impact on the social economy, cash waqf has been designated as one of the fastest-growing Islamic social finance topics. This study aims to synthesize all Elsevier-indexed research published over the past decade on the antecedents of cash waqf intention among Indonesian and Malaysian Muslims. Using systematic literature review, this article employs bibliometric methodology via the Biblioshiny platform and PRISMA framework where 87 articles were found to be knowledgeable about cash waqf between 2011 and 2023; after filtration with inclusion and exclusion criteria, 18 articles were found to be thoroughly reviewed. The results indicate that attitude, trust in the waqf institution, perceived behavioral control, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and convenience are the most influential factors on the intention to make a cash waqf contribution. This study also identified research gap concerning the antecedents of cash waqf intention for future research.*

Keywords: *Cash Waqf, Antecedents, Indonesia, Malaysia, SLR*

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is the country with the largest Muslim population (12.7%), followed by Pakistan (11.10%) and India (10.90%) (Population, 2023). Also, according to the 2018 CAF World Giving Index, Indonesians are the most generous donors (Charities Aid Foundation, 2022). This gives Indonesian Muslims enormous opportunities to participate in Islamic social finance, such as zakah, infaq, and waqf. According to the 2020 census, 61.3% of Malaysia's population, or 28.7 million people, are Muslims. Malaysia is now the fourth most populous country with a Muslim majority in the world. Malaysia is home to roughly 2.6% of the world's Muslim population as a percentage of the total population. Considering Malaysia's modest size, this is a substantial number (Malaysia, 2022). The prospective annual revenue of Indonesia's waqf industry, particularly cash waqf, is estimated to be 180 trillion rupiahs. According to the Indonesian Waqf Board, cash waqf acquisitions totaled 1,4 trillion rupiah as of March 2022. This quantity is greater than the 855 billion rupiah in cash waqf received from 2018 to 2021 (BWI, 2022). Meanwhile in Malaysia, after the introduction of the cash waqf concept, the waqf sector in Malaysia has witnessed explosive growth (Hasan et al., 2019). Since the establishment of Malaysia's Waqf Foundation and the introduction of new schemes for administering waqf assets through other associations, attitudes toward cash waqf have improved significantly, despite the inability to reach the desired level (Zakaria & Muda, 2017). According to Department of Awqaf, Zakat and Hajj (JAWHAR), Malaysia has many waqf lands totaling

11,091.82 hectares, including 4,836.5 hectares of general waqf and 6,255.32 hectares of special waqf.

Cash Waqf

Since the Ottoman Empire's era, monetary waqf has been a recognized notion. According to (Cizakca, 2004) the idea of cash waqf was crucial for the expansion of public revenues and significantly raised the socioeconomic standing of Muslims living throughout the Ottoman Empire. Imam Zufar, a member of the "Hanaf" School and an adherent of Abu Hanifah, authorized the dedication of all movable assets as waqf. In economic transactions based on *mudarabah*, he added the waqf of dirhams and dinars (monetary waqf), the return of which can be used for the waqf's charitable objectives (Al-Humam, 1988; Al-Tarabulsī, 1902; Ibn Ābidīn, 2003; Ibnu Qudamah, 1998). Additionally, Abu Yusuf (Ibn Ābidīn, 2003) and Imam Muhammad al-Shayban both agreed that any form of moveable property might be the subject of a waqf. Even though it is a cash waqf, Imam Malik bin Anas acknowledged that both immovable and moveable properties can be the subject of it. According to Maliki jurists, cash waqf, which is based on a loan without interest, is permitted (Al-Ābī, 1970). Imam Syafi'i and Ibn Hanbal, who represent the other two schools of Islamic law, concurred that both moveable and immovable property might be the subject of a waqf (Abū Zuhrah, 1959; Al-Zuhayli, 2002).

Muslim jurists have generally allowed the use of movable goods, such as cash and other financial assets, in the modern application of waqf. Cash endowment for waqf is acceptable, according to (Dewan Syariah Nasional MUI, 2014) one of the elements that has changed the focus on it is the belief of Imam Az-Zuhri (d. 124 H), who permitted the use of dinars and dirhams as waqf property for *da'wa* purposes and social objectives. Cash waqf is defined by the MUI as a waqf that can be performed by an individual, a group of individuals, an institution, or a legal organization in the form of cash (Dewan Syariah Nasional MUI, 2014).

Although there is an extensive amount of research on the antecedents or determinants of cash waqf intention behavior, there is no synthesis or systematic literature review (SLR) that summarises all the antecedents, including exploring all the variables on the same table, contrasting each hypothesis, and determining the extract or the best formula that motivates individuals to donate in cash waqf. The objective of this study is to synthesize the existing research on currency waqf in Indonesia and Malaysia. As evidenced by a scopus index literature review, Indonesia and Malaysia were the most prominent countries participating in cash waqf, followed by Turkey.

To accomplish this research objective, we conducted a systematic literature review and formulated the following research questions: (1) What are the antecedents or determining factors that may motivate individuals to make financial waqf gifts? (2) Who conducts the methodology and how? (3) What are the analyses of each antecedent that may have distinct correlations to the cash waqf intention? (4) What are the potential future research topics based on the gaps and novelties?

RESEARCH METHOD

The research was conducted on W1 July 2023, a Systematic Literature Review used in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. This method, according to (Liberati et al., 2009) comprises of the

following steps: (1) Defining eligibility criteria, (2) Defining information sources, (3) Study selection, (4) Data collection process, (5) Data item selection, (6) Eligibility criteria. The following inclusion criteria (IC) served as the guidelines for the systematic literature review. Study selection was conducted in three stages as follows: Using search keywords following the research objectives, namely, the determinants of sustainability reporting or other keywords of similar reports "Cash Waqf" OR "Wakaf Tunai" OR "Cash Islam* endowment" OR "Cash Islam* Social Finance") AND (LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Malaysia") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Indonesia") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Brunei Darussalam") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Singapore")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "Indonesian"), (2) Exploring and selecting the article titles, abstracts, and keywords based on the eligibility criteria. (3) Exploring and selecting all articles not eliminated in the previous selection by fully reading all articles while adhering to the eligibility criteria.

Figure 1. PRISMA Selection Method

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The search results in the Scopus database give output for 87 articles published in period of 2011 to H1'2023 written in English, Malaysian and Indonesian. On the premise of IC2 and IC3, the titles, abstracts, and keywords were used to examine and select 87 articles. The remaining 87 articles were subjected to a second screening based on IC2 and IC3 through a thorough perusal. Two articles could not be accessed, so it was added to the list of those we

eliminated or did not investigate. Following this procedure, 18 articles remained for further analysis.

Table 1. Biblioshiny Report Main Information

Description	Results
Timespan	2015:2023
Documents	18
Annual Growth Rate %	18.92
Authors	55
Authors of single-authored docs	2
Co-Authors per Doc	3.44
International co-authorships %	22.22

There are 18 documents pertinent to the objectives. This research has a high annual growth rate of 18.92% between 2015 and 2023, with an average citation per document of 7.6x and collaboration among 1,132 references involving 55 authors worldwide. The Journal of Islamic marketing was the first to publish on currency waqf determinants, followed by the Journal of Islamic monetary Economics and Finance and the International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management. In this study, Amin H was the most frequently cited local author, followed by Ajzen, who may have referred to the theory of planned behavior, and then Cizakca, who was born in Turkey and is a renowned researcher in the field of waqf field research. Universitas Sains Islam Malaysia, University of Indonesia, and University of Airlangga are the three institutions with the highest number of affiliations identified on cash waqf intentions. It is related to a biblioshiny report that Malaysia has become the most cited country in this study. By utilizing NVivo 12, words cloud analysis revealed a high frequency of research incorporating Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) variables into the framework.

Table 2. Research Studies of Cash Waqf Intention

Authors	Title	Theory Used	Qty of Antecedent
(Allah Pitchay et al., 2023)	A study of cash waqf contribution between millennials of Malaysia and Indonesia	Self Determination Theory (SDT)	4
(Masrizal et al., 2022)	Determinant factor of crowdfunders' behavior in using crowdfunding waqf model in Indonesia: two competing models	Combination TAM3 & UTAUT2	2
(Jatmiko et al., 2023)	Intergenerational analysis of cash waqf behavior: lessons learned from Indonesia	Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)	5
(Masrizal et al., 2023)	Investigating The Determinants of Cash Waqf Intention: An Insight from Muslims in Indonesia	Theory Reasoned Action (TRA)	3

(Allah Pitchay, 2022)	Factors influence intention of management of Shariah-compliant companies to participate in Islamic voluntary charity	Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)	4
(Pitchay et al., 2015)	Factors Influencing the Success of Retail Cash Waqf Linked Şukūk (CWLS) Issuance: A Lesson from Indonesia	Previous Empirical Studies	6
(Berakon, Aji, et al., 2022)	Impact of digital Sharia banking systems on cash-waqf among Indonesian Muslim youth	Combination TPB & TAM	4
(Berakon, Mutmainah, et al., 2022)	Muslim Intention to Participate In Retail Cwls: The Test Of Mediation And Moderation Effects	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	3
(Justine & Abd Jalil, 2022)	Repeated Giving Of Cash Waqf: A Case Study Of Sabah, Malaysia	Previous Empirical Studies	4
(Kasri & Chaerunnisa, 2022)	The role of knowledge, trust, and religiosity in explaining the online cash waqf amongst Muslim millennials	Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)	3
(Ab Shatar et al., 2021)	Determinants of cash waqf fund collection in Malaysian Islamic banking institutions: empirical insights from employees' perspectives	Theory Reasoned Action (TRA)	4
(Qurrata et al., 2020)	Media promotion, Islamic religiosity and Muslim community perception towards charitable giving of cash waqf	Marketing Literature	3
(Faturohman et al., 2020)	User Acceptance Of Online Waqf Applications: Evidence From Indonesia	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	4
(Abdul Shukor et al., 2019)	Trust on awqaf institutions: evidence from Malaysia	Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)	1
(Zabri & Mohammed, 2018)	Examining the behavioural intention to participate in a Cash Waqf-Financial Cooperative-Musharakah Mutanaqisah home financing model	Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)	3
(Shukor et al., 2017)	Muslim attitude towards participation in cash WAQF: Antecedents and consequences	Attitude	5
(Rizal & Amin, 2017)	Perceived ihsan, Islamic egalitarianism and Islamic religiosity towards charitable giving of cash waqf	Islamic Paradigm	3
(Pitchay et al., 2015)	Factors influencing the behavioral intentions of muslim employees to contribute to cash-waqf through salary deductions	Theory Reasoned Action (TRA)	2

These quantitative studies employ the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with AMOS, Lisrel, and PLS as the primary measurement instruments. In total, 10 broad theories are used

in research about the antecedents of cash waqf, with Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) being the most prevalent. From 18 articles which being studied, there are 68 variables which analyzed, whereas 48 variables were giving positive significant, 11 variables insignificant, 2 variables insignificant for each segment of Baby Boomer (BB) and gen X, and 2 variables insignificant for segment of Malaysian only. Attitude become the highest repetitive variables which commonly show as the positive significant antecedents to cash waqf intention, following by trust in waqf institution, perceived behavioral control (PBC), perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), and convenience.

Figure 2. Summarize Framework

A systematic review of the literature leads us to the conclusion that six variables have a significant influence on cash waqf intentions among Indonesian and Malaysian Muslims: (1) Attitude; (2) Trust in the Waqf Institution; (3) Perceived Behavioral Control; (4) Perceived Usefulness; (5) Perceived Ease of Use; and (6) Convenience. Other variables with positive significance to cash waqf intention include Financial Excess, Perception of Cash Waqf, Word of Mouth (WOM), Media Information, Variables from Theory Acceptance Model (TAM), Perceived Cost Advantage, Trust in Government, and Islamic Egalitarianism; however, these variables are discussed less frequently than the top six variables.

Face concern, Perceived Donor Effectiveness, a variable from the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Informative Influence, and Amount of Information were found to have statistically insignificant effects on cash waqf intentions. These provide a clear picture of how the cash waqf intention should be bolstered efficiently and effectively to place greater emphasis on the key objectives.

CONCLUSION

In modern Islamic social finance, cash waqf is the most essential instrument. In the past decade, numerous studies have focused on cash waqf, particularly on what motivates individuals to donate to cash waqf. This study utilized bibliometrics and Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

to analyze cash waqf literature and synthesize all findings pertaining to the precursors of cash waqf intention among Indonesian and Malaysian Muslims. The most frequently significant antecedents of cash waqf intention are (1) Attitude, (2) Trust in Waqf Intention, (3) Perceived Behavioral Control, (4) Perceived Usefulness, (5) Perceived Ease of Use, and (6) Convenience. Focusing on these factors can help Cash Waqf practitioners empower beneficiaries of cash waqf more efficiently and effectively. This study also focuses on potential future research that could bridge a substantial research gap for variables that vary from author to author, such as religiosity, subjective norm, knowledge/waqf literacy, moral obligation, and accessibility. There are also some limitations to this investigation. Scopus is the sole source of the database utilized for this investigation. From databases like Web of Science and Google Scholar, future research can be derived. This study only covers cash waqf, which does not specify whether it involves money or money waqf; additional research can use broader keywords to elucidate cash waqf in greater detail.

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